

Mode converters based on periodically perturbed waveguides for Mode Division Multiplexing

Diego Pérez-Galacho^{a,b}, Carlos Alonso-Ramos^a, Delphine Marris-Morini^a, Vladyslav Vakarin^a, Xavier Le Roux^a, and Laurent Vivien^a

^aCentre de Nanoscience et de Nanotechnology, CNRS, Univ. Paris-Sud, Universit Paris-Saclay, C2N-Orsay, 91405 Orsay Cedex, France

^bITEAM Research Institute, Universitat Politècnica de València, Valencia 46022, Spain

ABSTRACT

Bandwidth demands in optical communication systems are growing steadily and making Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) reach its limit. New multiplexing techniques are required in order to fulfill future bandwidth demands in next generation optical communications. Mode Division Multiplexing (MDM) has been recently proposed as good solution to increase aggregate bandwidth by multiplexing on the spatial domain. In this work we discuss the propositions of ultra-compact mode converters based on periodically perturbed waveguides. A corrugation (perturbation) is periodically inserted on one side of the waveguide. Each time the fundamental mode propagates through a perturbation a part of the incident light is transferred to the second mode. Around 5 periods are only needed to achieve complete power transfer, enabling for ultra-compact devices. Insertion loss below 0.5 dB and extinction ratio higher than 13 dB in the C-Band have been evaluated in a device with a total length of only 12 μm .

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays optical communication systems demand a steadily increasing bandwidth.^{1,2} However, maintaining a continuously growing bandwidth could not be done simply by scaling the electro-optical bandwidth of modulators and detectors. For that reason, multiplexing techniques are required in order to increase the aggregate bandwidth of a link. Orthogonality between different physical properties of light (like polarization or wavelength) are the base of multiplexing techniques. Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) and Polarization Division Multiplexing (PDM) are well known techniques widely used nowadays. The later exploit the polarization state of light (usually TE and TM) to multiplex data, while the first makes use of different wavelengths to transmit different data. However, future optical interconnects are expected to deliver bandwidths in the order of several hundreds of Tbps.² In that scenario WDM solutions will soon reach their limit and they would not be able to cope with that bandwidth demand anymore. Recently, a new orthogonality level based on the spatial distribution of optical field within a waveguide has been proposed.³ This technique, usually called Mode Division Multiplexing (MDM), uses the different optical modes of a waveguide to multiplex data. Current systems based on MDM make use of either fiber optics or free-space optics.^{4,5} However, in planar integrated technology MDM systems are not that developed. It will be desirable in the future to develop integrated photonics transceivers with mode diversity (i.e. MDM) monolithically integrated. In order to achieve that two basic building block are required; the Mode Multiplexer (MM) and the Mode Converter (MC). Some proposition of integrated photonics devices implementing the aforementioned functionalities appeared recently. There are three main physical mechanisms used to handle

Further author information: (Send correspondence to D. Pérez-Galacho)

D. Pérez-Galacho: E-mail: diepega@upv.es

C. Alonso-Ramos: E-mail: carlos.ramos@u-psud.fr

D. Marris-Morini: E-mail: delphine.morini@u-psud.fr

V. Vakarin: E-mail: vladyslav.vakarin@u-psud.fr

X. Le Roux: E-mail: xavier.leroux@u-psud.fr

L. Vivien: E-mail: laurent.vivien@u-psud.fr

modes in a waveguides: evanescent coupling, mode evolution and multimode interferometry. MDM devices based on evanescent coupling normally are implemented by means of Directional Coupler^{6–10} and ring resonators.^{11,12} Mode evolution based MDM devices use Y-junctions.^{13–15} Multimode Interference (MMI) couplers are based on multimode interferometry, they have been proposed for implementing MM and MC.^{16–21} Periodic waveguides have been recently proposed to implement MDM functionalities.^{22–24} In this work we propose an ultracompact MC based on periodically perturbed waveguide in a standard silicon on insulator (SOI) technological platform. This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 the principle of operation of the device is presented and discussed. Section 3 is devoted to the design of an ultra-compact mode converter. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the main conclusions of this work.

2. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

The working principle of the device is based on periodically patterning one side of a waveguide that support two modes, as represented in Fig. 1. When the first order mode reaches a discontinuity, a part of the power is coupled into the second mode. Properly designing the periodic pattern if it possible to achieve full transformation from the first to the second order mode.

Figure 1. Top view of the mode converter base on lateral waveguide grating.

In order to illustrate how this kind of devices work, we consider a standar 220 nm-thick SOI technology with an air cladding. Firstly the width of the waveguide is set to 750 nm in order to guarantee that first and the second order modes can propagate and the third order mode is in cut-off. In order to understand how the device work the side perturbation of the waveguide (Δw) is set to only 25 nm. Using this small perturbation the excitation of the second order mode is reduced, facilitating the study of the structure. In order to further facilitate the study of the structure the perturbations are considered abrupt, i.e. there is no transition between one width and the other. The structure was then simulated using the EME approach of Lumerical,²⁵ that enables to obtain the response of an arbitrary number of periods analyzing only one. The length of each section (wide and narrow) was set to match the beat length ($L_{\text{beat}} = \pi/\beta_1 - \beta_2$) between the first and second order modes. Then, the S parameters of the structure were calculated as a function of the number of periods. Results are plotted in Fig. 2. It can be seen that full conversion is achieved for 19 periods, it can also be seen that the conversion follows a cosine relation with the number of periods. This cosine relation is in fact a decaying cosine due to the fact that due to the abrupt discontinuity in each period a part of the power is lost due to mode mismatch. It is important to point out that with a perturbation of only 25 nm full mode conversion is achieved with only 19 periods, what leads to a total length of $\sim 46 \mu\text{m}$. This demonstrate that not only it is possible to obtain full mode conversion with this approach, but also it exhibits potential to do it very efficiently.

3. 1ST TO 2ND ULTRACOMPACT MODE CONVERTER DESIGN

In order to fully exploit the efficiency of this approach we consider now a perturbation of 150 nm. In order to minimize loss due to mode mismatch, a transition with some slope is considered instead of an abrupt change. This means that the side perturbation are no longer rectangles but trapezoids. Before taking into account the transitions, a structure with abrupt width changes was simulated, the curves from Fig. 3 (a) were obtained. The cosine dependence of the curves can be seen, however due to the discrete nature of the number of periods it is not possible to obtain full conversion. Full conversion is between 3 and 4 periods. Taking the transitions now into consideration, the length of the transition provides an additional degree of freedom that can be used not only for reducing the loss but also to lower a bit the efficiency of each perturbation so full conversion match an

integer number of periods. Optimizing the transition length, curves of Fig. 3 (b) are obtained. It is now possible to see that full conversion matches exactly with 4 periods. This leads to a device that is able to fully convert from first to second order mode with a length of less than 12 μm .

Figure 2. S parameters of the mode converter based on lateral waveguide grating as a function of the number of periods.

Figure 3. S parameters of the mode converter based on lateral waveguide grating as a function of the number of periods: (a) without transitions, (b) with transitions.

This final device was then simulated using FDTD. The spectral response of Fig. 4 was obtained, where the propagation of the first order mode ($|S_{21}|^2$ 1st \leftrightarrow 1st mode) and the conversion into the second order mode ($|S_{21}|^2$

1st \leftrightarrow 2nd mode) are represented. The obtained insertion loss (IL) from the simulation was below 0.5 dB in the whole wavelength simulation range. It can also be seen that the bandwidth of operation for 20 dB extinction ratio (ER) is 23 nm and the ER is higher than 13 dB in the whole C-Band. In Fig. 4 (b) the propagated electric field at a wavelength of 1.55 μm is shown. It is possible to see how each perturbations excite a bit of the second order mode until and the end of the device almost only the second order mode remains.

Figure 4. FDTD simulation results of the mode converter based on lateral waveguide grating: (a) spectral response, (b) propagated field at a wavelength of 1.55 μm .

Even though the device presented has been implemented using trapezoids as periodic perturbations, it is possible to use any kind of periodic perturbation in one side. Some examples can be a sinusoidal modulation of one side of the waveguide or a periodic reduction of one side of the waveguide (bitten-like waveguide).

4. CONCLUSIONS

A mode converter based on periodically perturbed waveguide has been proposed. Its principle of operation has been explained in detail and its design has been presented, leading to an ultra-compact device of only 12 μm long. The device exhibit an outstanding performance making it suitable for future Mode Division Multiplex optical communication systems.

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